

Attitudes among students of institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities towards entrepreneurship

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Abstract

The Object of the study aims to identify the attitudes of students of the institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities towards entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial activity, and to identify the differences between students in attitudes according to the institutes concerned with the study, for this purpose, we used the descriptive method in the form of a survey, On a sample composed of 185 students Chosen as stratified random, and for data collection, we used a tool designed for the same purpose (a questionnaire of attitudes according to the emotional, cognitive behavioral dimension), which was distributed electronically. After collecting the results and having treated them statistically, we conclude That the students have attitudes towards entrepreneurship and that there are differences between students in the attitudes towards entrepreneurship according to the institutes concerned with the study. On this basis, the study recommended Increasing number of courses that qualify university youth for self-employment and entrepreneurial projects, and overcoming all obstacles in that.

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Introduction

Most research in the field of entrepreneurship is based on two main theories the theory of planned behavior and the entrepreneurial event theory that is widely used by researchers who ask about intended behaviour, According to Fishbein and Ajzen, orientation is the best predictor of behavior, as it determines the probability of implementing the behaviour, Sokol and Shapero (1975-1982) are considered among the most important pioneers in the field of entrepreneurship through their adoption of the most famous model in entrepreneurship, It is known as the event model, which explains the entrepreneurship event through the elements of explaining the choice of entrepreneurship path rather than any other career, It is based on the concept of transformations (negative, positive, intermediate) that change the course of life. (Amin and Kaltouma, 2019)

Shapiro (1982) developed a model on the factors affecting entrepreneurial intentions and the tendency to establish private enterprises. His contribution concluded that the trend towards entrepreneurship is governed by three basic factors: Realization of desire and realizing the inclinations, as well as the perceived feasibility, As the desire and feasibility of work are among the most important factors affecting the individual's intention to start the project. This trend is supported by the extent of awareness of desire and the availability of self-efficacy Which represents one of the important foundations for building the tendency towards entrepreneurship and the implementation of the project in particular. (Layla and Zahra, 2019)

The issue of establishing private institutions or attempting to establish entrepreneurial projects has become an important matter that occupies a large part of the interests of scholars and specialists in various economic, social and psychological fields, Where one of the specialized scientists says that entrepreneurship will be the largest economic force humanity has known so far, Recently, researchers and practitioners have increased interest in entrepreneurial wealth (the small enterprise sector), Entrepreneurship was able to invade various fields, until it became a specialty taught in universities, The process of transforming innovative ideas into pioneering projects capable of growth and prosperity in order to achieve sustainable qualitative development will be the biggest challenge facing the country in general and the university in particular. (Ibrahim and Mansour, 2019).

Therefore, Algerian universities are trying to make unremitting efforts as part of the government's directions to cultivate the entrepreneurial spirit and enhance the entrepreneurial orientation among university students. (Ibrahim and Ghayat, 2020) Where students (students of the institutes of science and

technology of physical and sports activities in our study) who have creative ideas to create investment institutions within the framework of entrepreneurial sports thought can translate their creative ideas if they have sufficient financial support provided by the bodies charged with supporting youth investments to create mini-enterprises in all fields. (Nour al-Din and al-Hadj, 2021) In view of the ambiguity surrounding the sports entrepreneurial field... Based on all of the above, the researcher decided to carry out this study with the aim of identifying entrepreneurship among students of the institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities through trends towards entrepreneurial activity and the differences between students in that.

1.1. Literature Review: There are many studies that dealt with this topic from different angles, including **the study of Nasri Muhammad al-Sharif and others (2021)** entitled: Tendencies towards entrepreneurship among Female students of institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities. The study aimed to identify the level of tendencies towards entrepreneurship among female students of science and technology of physical and sports activities, And the differences according to the university of study (Souk Ahras / Annaba) and according to the place of residence (inside the center of the state / outside the center of the state). To achieve the aim of the study, a stratified random sample of 69 female students from Souk Ahras and Annaba universities was selected, A questionnaire designed by the researchers was distributed. The study concluded that the female students have moderate tendencies towards entrepreneurship, With no statistically significant differences in the level of tendencies towards entrepreneurship, according to the variables of the study. The researchers recommended the need to include some subjects in the program to raise the entrepreneurial skills of students, And holding information days to show the facilities and support provided by the state to women's entrepreneurship. (Muhammad Al-Sharif and others, 2021) And I dealt with **the study of Abdali Noureddine, Qadri Al-Hajj, (2021)** entitled: Entrepreneurial sports orientation for students of science and technology of physical and sports activities, University of Batna 2, according to the Shapiro and Sokol model, Where the study aimed to find out the orientation of students of science and techniques of physical and sports activities to work within the sports entrepreneurial field, It examines the extent to which there is a desire, ability and inclination to establish a sports entrepreneurial project within the Dimensions of the Entrepreneurial

Event Model of Shapiro and Sokol. The two researchers used the exploratory descriptive approach on a study population consisting of (200) master students from the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of Batna 2, The questionnaire was distributed electronically to a sample of (130) students. In the study, a questionnaire was used to measure the students' tendency to enter the field of entrepreneurship in the sports field, The study concluded that the students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities have a tendency to invest in the sports entrepreneurial field, And that there are actual inclinations and desire among the students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities to initiate the establishment of a sports entrepreneurial project, However, the position of the studied sample was neutral regarding their ability to embody a sports entrepreneurial project. (Nour al-Din and al-Hadj, 2021) **The study of Ibrahim Bidd El Kawle and Tijani Mansour (2018)** was entitled: University students' attitudes towards entrepreneurial activity, The study aimed to identify the level of university students' attitudes towards entrepreneurial activity, Knowing the level of grades of students according to the determinants of the entrepreneurial orientation And the detection of differences between the Genders in the level of orientation towards entrepreneurship. The study followed the descriptive approach on a study population represented by undergraduate students at the University of Djelfa on a sample of 50 male and female students, they were randomly selected during the academic year 2017/2018. The study used a scale designed by the researcher (Ibrahim Beid Alkol) after reviewing and being guided by many studies and standards that dealt with the entrepreneurial orientation. The results of the study concluded that the sample members of university students have a high level of orientation towards entrepreneurial work (establishing a private enterprise) and that there are no statistically significant differences between males and females in the total degree of entrepreneurial orientation, The study also showed that there is a difference in students' scores according to the determinants of entrepreneurial orientation it showed that the level of each of the desire, attitude and social environment was high among the students, The study concluded that there were no statistically significant differences between the genders. (Ibrahim and Mansour, 2019) As for **the study of Saleh Awad Al-Jahdali (2022)**, entitled: Youth attitudes towards entrepreneurship to confront the problem of unemployment in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study aimed to identify the general trends of university youth towards entrepreneurship

projects to confront the problem of unemployment in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia through three aspects (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral), identifying the factors influencing his attitudes, and identifying the difficulties he faces, The study used the social survey method by selecting a proportional stratified random sample from the study population where 5 colleges were randomly selected to represent the strata of society, Of the male and female students, a simple random sample was selected representing the study community, the size of which is (368) male and female students. The study used a questionnaire for a sample of "university youth" and a semi-standardized interview tool with "experts" as data collection tools prepared by the researcher. The results of the study showed that university youth agree with the general trends towards entrepreneurship projects to confront the problem of unemployment in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Where the emotional aspect ranked first, followed by the behavioral aspect in the second, and finally the cognitive aspect came in the third rank. (Wajdan Saleh, 2022) **From all this, the question of our study came as follows:** Are there trends towards entrepreneurship among students of institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities?

And are there any differences between the students of the Algerian institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities in the attitudes towards entrepreneurship according to the one-way analysis of variance?

2.Method and Materials:

independent variable: Attitudes among students of institutes of science and technology for physical and sports activities.

dependent variable: Entrepreneurship.

The selection of the sample is one of the most important problems facing the researcher, The scientific results depend on the extent to which the sample represents the indigenous community and all its groups, Due to the nature of the subject and its variables, the sample was selected using the "stratified random method". Where (Ahmed Badr) indicates that "the researcher's goal in this sample is to be representative of the various groups or homogeneous classes in the society to be measured or surveyed."..... The size of the class is proportional to the size of the class in the original society... We should also point out that the vocabulary is also chosen randomly from these strata so that the probability of representing each unit of these groups in the sample increases, At the same time, all the characteristics of a random sample are present. (Ahmed, 1996) A sample of students from the Institutes of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities was selected

for the academic year 2019/2020, The final research sample consisted of (185) male and female students.

2.1. Participants

Table No. (01): shows the distribution of the participants respondents according to the study institute

The institute/university	the number	percentage%
Muhammad Al-Sharif Musadia (Souk Ahras)	55	29,72
Mohamed Boudiaf (Al-Masila)	60	32,43
Ammar Thalji (Laghout)	40	21,62
Hassiba Benbouali (Chlef)	30	16,21
the total	185	100.0

-The problem of our study required the use of the descriptive approach. It is, as Vandlin points out, the method that searches for accurate descriptions of processes and phenomena, and is based on depicting the current situation....(faouzi and others, 2021)

2.2. Materials. - Questionnaire of Trends towards entrepreneurship.

The cognitive school divides trends in social psychology into three elements (components): A cognitive component, an emotional and sentimental component, an intentional or behavioral component, or a behavioral tendency towards action, And there are those who take into account all the components in its definition and see that trends are the individual's inclinations or acquired inclinations in his positive or negative response towards the individual, behaviour, belief or product. This definition is the most comprehensive. The attitudes that the individual holds about a certain thing will affect his decision towards this thing. If a person has positive attitudes towards a particular idea, we can expect that he is more inclined to implement that idea among the many alternatives. But if he carries negative attitudes about a certain idea, then we can expect that this person will be inclined not to adopt this idea. (Hassan Ali, 1990)

2.3. Design and Procedure. Based on this, and after reviewing several relevant measures, questionnaires, studies and models, our study tool (a questionnaire of entrepreneurship trends) consisted of three components, A cognitive component whose statements range from 1-10, an emotional component whose statements range from 11-20, and a behavioral component whose statements range from 21-29, Formulated using a Likert scale and all statements were in the positive direction, and they are corrected as follows: Not completely applicable = 1 degree, weakly applicable = 2 degrees, moderately applicable = 3 degrees, highly applicable = 4 degrees, fully applicable = 5 degrees.

-Psychometric characteristics of the study tool: (questionnaire of attitudes towards entrepreneurship): The validity was calculated by presenting the questionnaire to a group of experts, whereby some phrases that were not in line with the general context of the questionnaire were deleted and modified, according to the agreement of the experts, The validity of the tool was also confirmed by calculating the validity of the internal consistency of attitudes towards entrepreneurship, It is the correlation coefficient between the sub-components (cognitive, sentimental, behavioral) with the total value of attitudes towards entrepreneurship, This is after subjecting all the statements of the three components (cognitive- sentimental -behavioral) to the validity of the internal consistency and the stability of Cronbach's alpha.

Table No. (02) shows the validity of the internal consistency of the trends towards entrepreneurship Students of science and technology physical and sports activities

Directions subcomponents	Trends towards entrepreneurship	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	Pearson Correlation
Cognitive	.000	.849**
sentimental	.000	.837**
behaviourist	.000	.828**

Through Table No. (02) It turns out that the questionnaire has good internal consistency since all sub-components (cognitive, emotional, behavioral) are strongly correlated statistically at 0.01 with the total value of attitudes towards entrepreneurship among students of science and technology of physical and sports activities.

-Stability: We used alpha stratified stability to measure the stability of attitudes towards entrepreneurship, and we found a stability coefficient estimated at 0.910, which is a good stability coefficient.

For reference, the tool (Trends Questionnaire) was distributed electronically through electronic links, private emails, and various possible electronic media, in addition to collecting data on a field basis as possible due to the conditions of the Corona pandemic.

2.4. Statistical Analysis. Arithmetic mean - standard deviation – percentages- Correlation to calculate the validity of internal consistency - Cronbach's alpha coefficient for calculating the stability coefficient of internal consistency- Stratified alpha coefficient for calculating the reliability of the overall questionnaire - One-way analysis of variance test.

3. Results.

Table No. (03) It shows the differences between the students of the institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities in the attitudes towards entrepreneurship according to a one-way analysis of variance

variable	source of contrast	sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	mean of squares	value (F)	value Sig	Appreciation
Trends towards entrepreneurs hip	between groups	9747.01	3	1392.43	6.27	0.00	There is a significance at 0.01
	within groups	38429.32	181	111.065			
	the total	48352.33	184				

Sig value < 0,01

Through table No. (03) it is clear that there are statistically significant differences in the attitudes towards entrepreneurship among students of science and technology of physical and sports activities in the institutes This is at an estimated significance of 0.01 Whereas, the value of F is equal to 6.27, and the value of Sig is equal to 0.00, which is less than the significance of 0.01.

Table No. (04) represents the descriptive statistics of institute students in attitudes towards entrepreneurship, according to the variable of the study institute.

The institute/university	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	arrangement
Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of Laghouat	98.50	20.43	1
Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, Souk Ahras University	92.35	13.53	2
Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, Chlef University	85.53	12.86	3
Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of M'sila	80.80	17.84	4
the total	87.29	18.16	/

Through Table No. (04), which shows the descriptive statistics of the trends towards entrepreneurship according to the institutes, it is clear that:

1. Students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of Laghouat, rank first in attitudes towards entrepreneurship, with an arithmetic mean of 98.50 and a standard deviation of 20.43.
2. Students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, Souk Ahras University, rank second in attitudes towards entrepreneurship, with an arithmetic mean of 92.35 and a standard deviation of 13.53.
3. Students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of Chlef, ranked third in attitudes towards entrepreneurship, with an arithmetic mean of 85.53 and a standard deviation of 12.86.
4. Students of the Institute of Science and Techniques of Physical and Sports Activities at M'sila University rank fourth in attitudes towards entrepreneurship, with an arithmetic mean of 80.80 and a standard deviation of 17.84.

4. Discussion. The results of our study showed that there are trends towards entrepreneurship among students of the Institutes of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities. And that there are differences among students in their attitudes towards entrepreneurship, according to the institutes concerned with the study, This can be explained and attributed to the results of most of the studies conducted in this field, including the study (Ibrahim and Mansour, 2019) which indicated that there was a high level of students' orientation and their intention to establish private institutions to enter the labor market and find alternatives to the public job, And they are aware of the extent of responsibilities required by such entrepreneurial

projects. This is also indicated by the study (Wejdan, 2022) that university youth are motivated towards their attitudes, ideas, beliefs, values, behavior, and stable feelings towards awareness of entrepreneurship and its importance and role in the independence of the individual and achieving self-sufficiency for him. This confirms the consistency of their attitudes in the three components (emotional, behavioral and cognitive) it confirms the strong desire and high level of self-conviction among young people towards entrepreneurship projects. The study (Ibrahim and Ghayat, 2018) also showed that there is an indication of a high level of entrepreneurial orientation and entry into the labor market, which gives us strong indications that university students are highly motivated to establish their own projects. Our study agrees with the study of (Nour al-din and al-Hadj, 2021), which concluded that the students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities have a tendency to invest in the sports entrepreneurial field, and that there are actual inclinations and desire among the students of the Institute of Science and Technology for physical and sports activities to initiate the establishment of a sports entrepreneurship project. It is also consistent with the study (Ibrahim and Mansour, 2019), the results of which concluded that a sample of university students have a high level of orientation towards entrepreneurship (creating a private project). It also agrees with the study (Wajdan, 2022), which showed that university youth agree with the general trends towards entrepreneurship projects to confront the problem of unemployment in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, This result, according to the same study, is explained by the fact that young people see that entrepreneurship projects meet their future aspirations, and therefore we find that they feel safe if they are associated with working in entrepreneurship projects, And that young people see that entrepreneurial projects achieve independence for them in work, and that the majority of them prefer entrepreneurial projects over other businesses in order to achieve for them their being, self, and social status within society. A study (Muhammad Fawaz and Abd-Razzaq, 2019) showed that the students' attitude towards creating an institution is positive, and that the personal criterion and the perceived behavioral control positively affect the entrepreneurial intent of the students. As for the study (Wasila and Abbas, 2020), it was concluded that the majority of the questioned students want and seriously think about starting small projects of their own. The study (Nour El-Din and Al-Hajj, 2021) concluded that the students of the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, Batna University 2, have a positive tendency to invest in the

sports entrepreneurial field, and they have the actual desire and inclination to start establishing a sports entrepreneurship project. We agree with the study (Sidi Mohamed and others, 2018), which concluded that the majority of the students questioned want to start their own small projects, as well as the study (Nour Al-Huda and Khawla 2020), which concluded that the fulfillment of desire contributes significantly to the formation of the entrepreneurial intention. Thus, students have actual inclinations to start establishing private investment projects. On the other hand, the researcher attributes the differences in students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship according to the institutes to what was indicated by the study (Munira and Youssef, 2010) that the entrepreneurial orientation is a state of mind whereby the individual tends to create a new facility or a new value within existing organizations, An entrepreneurial orientation is an individual will or intellectual readiness that turns into establishing an enterprise, under certain conditions. Krueger (1993) considers the tendency to work as one of the factors influencing the intention of entrepreneurship. This is what we have seen, and it is present among the members of the sample researched by virtue of the nature and environment of the existence of these institutes, We can attribute these differences between students and between institutes as well, according to the study (Ibrahim and Ghayat, 2020) to the personal attraction of the study sample by virtue of the nature of the school subjects it is also related to the extent to which each of the family and friends appreciates such decisions related to the labor market and sustainable development, which benefits the individual and his surroundings and achieves psychological and social adjustment for them. The set of personal characteristics and characteristics of an individual, in addition to environmental factors, play a role in influencing the individual's behavior and attitudes towards entrepreneurship and self-employment, especially among university students, Therefore, the tendency to start a contracting business is a prerequisite for an individual to become an entrepreneur. The researcher attributes the differences in the attitudes towards entrepreneurship among students according to the institutes as well to the findings of the study (Boubaker Al-Siddiq, 2017), which showed that the study sample had positive attitudes towards the idea of entrepreneurship, It was also found that the students' social environment has a role in influencing the students in the entrepreneurial act, and the level of the entrepreneurial spirit was high for the sample students, In addition, the sample students have a good level of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills

that were provided to them during the formation of their university, which motivates and encourages them to go into the field of entrepreneurship. The differences between students according to institutes can also be attributed to a group of factors, as the study (Wajdan, 2022) indicated that university youth do not receive sufficient guidance regarding the procedures for taking a loan to finance the graduate, which reduced their ability to know these procedures, This result provides an opportunity to shed light on university youth by the family, the university and society in general to develop the culture of entrepreneurship projects and to clarify the procedures for taking financing loans. This result explains that there are no guidance and counseling programs dedicated to introducing young people to the basics of building entrepreneurial projects, which reduced their knowledge of the basics of building these projects. A study (Wajdan, 2022) showed that some young people's adherence to the idea of obtaining a government job instead of working in entrepreneurial projects makes them not inclined towards entrepreneurship projects and have negative attitudes towards them. And that some of the customs and traditions of the community are compatible with some pioneering projects, which provides community support for young people and enhances their attitudes towards entrepreneurship while some customs and traditions are not compatible with other projects, which creates negative attitudes towards young people. Young people's feeling that it is difficult for them to assume the responsibility of an entrepreneurial project on their own increases their fear of the demand for these projects, which increases the difficulties they face towards working in entrepreneurial projects because they are new to this work and to prevent risk. This applies to a large extent to some institutes in our study, and therefore these differences appeared between the institutes. Our study differs from the study of (Laila and Al-Zahra, 2019), which concluded that there is an average level of students towards the entrepreneurial orientation and the study (Al-Khazaleh, 2018), which concluded that the attitudes of university students towards self-employment were moderate, the study also showed that the role of the university in developing youth attitudes towards self-employment was weak. The study (Al-moadine and Al-Qasim 2020) concluded that there are obstacles facing young people related to the adoption of small projects, the weak financial capabilities to adopt small projects, and the high percentage of loans granted to these projects, And the scarcity of specialized devices in the field of marketing for small projects. All of this showed these differences in trends between the institutes.

5. Conclusion. Through conducting this study, it was found that there are actual and intentional attitudes among students of the institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities towards entrepreneurial activity and the establishment of small enterprises. This was generally among the students, but these trends differ according to the institutes of study, due to several circumstances and reasons previously mentioned in the discussion. Accordingly, the researcher recommends and suggests the need to include some subjects in educational programs to raise students' entrepreneurship skills, And holding information days to show the facilities and support provided by the state, and activating the role of the entrepreneurial house at the level of institutes of science and technology for physical and sports activities and the inclusion of standards and units concerned with entrepreneurial education among students in the institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities. This was recommended by several studies, including (the study of Muhammad al-Sharif and others, 2021) Spreading awareness, refining skills, and raising the state of knowledge, a large part of it falls on the educational bodies, and this is what (Boudabbous, 2011) refers to, Where he emphasized the two currencies, training and training, that they are necessary to achieve private entrepreneurship, hence the importance of the education system, whose mission is to raise awareness, prepare and train for entrepreneurship.

- Establishing electronic platforms specialized in following up these ideas from their initial registration until the stage of adoption and implementation in the field.
- Programming courses that qualify university youth for self-employment and entrepreneurial projects.
- Overcoming all administrative, financial and legal obstacles that stand in the way of students who are about to start their entrepreneurial projects, and work to find regular outlets to market their products.
- Where he indicated in this regard (Younes and others, 2020) that the owner of a private sports project is always looking for a share in the market, and this is only done if the owner of the project follows a correct scientific method that guarantees his products a position in the market or attracts a large number of customers.
- Shed light in future studies on university youth and the role of the family, the university and society in general to develop the culture of entrepreneurial projects and clarify the procedures for taking financing loans and conducting research and studies in this field by presenting successful models of entrepreneurial projects and referring to possible job opportunities in establishing small enterprises to encourage those with creative ideas.

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